

Regioselective synthesis of bioactive heterocycles by radical cyclization[†]

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Abstract : In recent years free radical cyclization has emerged as one of the versatile and simplest methodology for the construction of carbon-carbon bond in organic synthesis. In multi-step synthesis its use is significant as the key step of the synthesis involve the formation of carbon-carbon or carbon-hetero bond employing radical cyclization strategy. Regioselective synthesis of heterocycles viz. uracil, pyrone, coumarin, quinolone indole, benzofuran-annulated oxygen, nitrogen and sulfur heterocyclic compounds by tri-*n*-butyl tin hydride and thiol-mediated radical cyclization will be presented.

Keywords : Endowment lecture, regioselective synthesis, heterocycles, bioactive, radical cyclization.

1. Introduction

Recently, free radical cyclization has emerged as a versatile route for the construction of carbocycles as well as heterocycles¹. These results underscore the importance of developing new methods for the synthesis of various heterocycles², which may be achieved by constructing five-, six-member and larger rings, either in separate or multistep processes. Since their first appearance in literature, various types of *exo*- and *endo*-cyclizations of radicals onto internal unsaturated bonds have been emphasized. Beckwith^{3a} and Stork^{3b} reported that under tin hydride mediated reaction condition 5-*exo*/6-*endo* type of vinyl radical cyclization onto C=C bond gives a mixture of both 5-*exo* and 6-*endo* products. The kinetic study of Beckwith^{3a} also showed that the initially formed five-membered ring radical undergoes further isomerisation to produce the six-membered ring. The fact that the five-membered ring closure is kinetically favoured⁴ and is further supported by the work of Crich *et al.* They pointed out the preferential formation of 5-*exo* products by carrying out the reaction in very rapid radical quenching system using PhSeSePh-Bu₃SnH (Fig. 1). Similar observation was found in case of acyl radical⁵ where a 5-*exo*/6-*endo* acyl radical cyclization also gives a mixture of both 5-*exo* and 6-*endo* products and accordingly, the 5-*exo* cyclization of acyl radical on to a C=C bond is a kineti-

cally favoured process (Fig. 2). The search for various heterocycles and many new methodologies has been a central goal for free radical chemists in recent years.

Fig. 1. Vinyl radical cyclizations onto C=C.

Fig. 2. Acyl radical cyclizations onto C=C.

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2. Reagents, solvents and initiators used in radical reaction

Although different organotin reagents are available for radical reaction⁶, tri-*n*-butyltin hydride has been proven to be a most useful radical generating reagent. The alternative procedure involving the use of small amount of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride with sodium cyanoborohydride for *in situ* generation of tri-*n*-butyltin hydride is also known. But it is not useful in pharmaceutical synthesis due to its high toxicity⁷. Additionally it is very difficult to remove the tributyltin residues from the reaction mixtures. Purification of products is, therefore, very difficult and various attempts have been made to overcome this problem. Due to this problem various efforts have been directed towards the tin free radical chemistry⁸. Tributylgermanium hydride (Bu₃GeH)⁹ is the superior alternatives to ⁿBu₃SnH, devoid of all these problems. Use of tris(trimethylsilyl)silane [(TMS)₃SiH or TTMSS]⁹ and polymethylhydrosiloxanes¹⁰ have been extensively developed. Although in most cases AIBN is used as radical initiator, substantial use of other diazine initiators, e.g. AMBN [azobis(methylisobutyronitrile)] in radical reactions is also reported. It is more soluble and can be used in cyclohexane as well as toluene as solvent. Cyclohexane is found to be the preferred solvent for ⁿBu₃SnH mediated reactions because toluene and benzene not only act as a solvent but also may participate in radical reactions.

Owing to have the advantage from the point of view of its cost, safety and environmental concern the use of water¹¹, as a solvent, is a tremendous development in the field of radical cyclization. Additionally, most of the organic radical species are stable in water. Indium metal can also be used for tandem carbon-carbon bond forming reaction as a single electron transfer radical initiator in aqueous medium¹².

The reaction is best carried out by using various surfactants (e.g. CTAB) in the presence of VA-061 and EPHP. Recently, Barton *et al.* have reported a radical reaction using hypophosphorous acid¹³. A novel radical reduction in aqueous isopropyl alcohol using the combination of VA-061, hypophosphorous acid and triethyl amine was reported by Kita *et al.*¹⁴. Triethylborane (Et₃B) is a powerful reagent for radical cyclisation and the novel tandem radical addition cyclization of oxime ethers and hydrazones

intramolecularly concerted with the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group was also demonstrated¹⁵. Diethyl phosphite, (EtO)₂P(O)H, was proved to be an useful alternative and more versatile reagent for radical cyclisation¹⁶. For the last few years Ce^{IV} reagents (ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) and ceric-tetra-*n*-butylammonium nitrate (CTAN)) are widely applied for the generation of the radicals and radical cations for the construction of carbon-carbon bonds which have been exemplified in the oxidative additions of 1,3-dicarbonyl substrates to allyltrimethylsilane¹⁷.

3. Synthesis of oxygen heterocycles

The synthesis of tetrahydrofurans by the radical cyclization of bromo acetals and bromo ketals is well known. Srikrishna *et al.*¹⁸ have utilized the tributyltin hydride mediated radical cyclization reaction to produce the 2,3,5-tri- and 2,3,4,5-tetrasubstituted furans, respectively. Zhang *et al.*¹⁹ reported a novel double *ipso*-substitution process for the synthesis of azabenzisocoumarins. They also reported²⁰ a straightforward two-step parallel synthesis for structurally diverse spiro compounds, where 2-bromobenzoic acids were used as the common building blocks to couple with a series of conjugated enols or enamines. Sequential intramolecular free radical Michael addition led to the formation of spirobenzolactones, spirobenzolactams, spirobenzolactone-lactams, spirobenzolactone-thiolactones, spirodilactones and bridged-spirolactones.

Recently, we have reported²¹ the regioselective synthesis of 1*H*,3*H*,6*H*-[2]benzopyrano[4,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2,4-diones **3a-f** (75–85%) and 12*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*]₁]benzopyran-5-ones **4a-h** (70–85%), respectively, by radical cyclization reactions.

The starting materials, the 5-(2-bromobenzyloxy)pyrimidine-2,4-ones **1a-f** and 4-(2-bromobenzyloxy)-benzopyran-7-ones **2a-h**, were separately refluxed under a nitrogen atmosphere with tri-*n*-butyltin chloride and sodium cyanoborohydride in the presence of a catalytic amount of AIBN for 3–4 h to give the cyclic products **3a-f** or **4a-h**, respectively (Scheme 1).

We have also extended our efforts²² in the regioselective synthesis of 2*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*]quinolin-7(8*H*)-ones **6a-f** by the ⁿBu₃SnH-mediated radical cyclization of 4-(2-bromobenzyloxy)quinolin-2(1*H*)-one derivatives **5a-f** (Scheme 2).

- 3(a) $R^1 = R^2 = \text{CH}_3$, $R^3 = \text{H}$ (80%)
 (b) $R^1 = R^2 = \text{CH}_3$, $R^3 = \text{OCH}_3$ (75%)
 (c) $R^1 = R^2 = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $R^3 = \text{H}$ (85%)
 (d) $R^1 = R^2 = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $R^3 = \text{OCH}_3$ (80%)
 (e) $R^1 = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $R^2 = \text{CH}_3$, $R^3 = \text{H}$ (82%)
 (f) $R^1 = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $R^2 = \text{CH}_3$, $R^3 = \text{OCH}_3$ (84%)

- 4(a) $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = R^4 = \text{H}$ (75%)
 (b) $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = \text{H}$, $R^4 = \text{OMe}$ (78%)
 (c) $R^1 = R^3 = R^4 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{Me}$ (70%)
 (d) $R^1 = R^3 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{Me}$, $R^4 = \text{OMe}$ (80%)
 (e) $R^1 = R^3 = \text{Me}$, $R^2 = R^4 = \text{H}$ (76%)
 (f) $R^1 = R^3 = \text{Me}$, $R^2 = \text{H}$, $R^4 = \text{OMe}$ (85%)
 (g) $R^1 = R^2 = R^4 = \text{H}$, $R^3 = \text{Me}$ (82%)
 (h) $R^1 = R^2 = \text{H}$, $R^3 = \text{Me}$, $R^4 = \text{OMe}$ (78%)

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions : (i) $n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$, $\text{Na}(\text{CN})\text{BH}_3$, AIBN, benzene, reflux, 4 h; (ii) $n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$, $\text{Na}(\text{CN})\text{BH}_3$, AIBN, benzene, reflux, 3–4 h.

- 6(a) $R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = -\text{CH}_3$ (70%)
 (b) $R^1 = -\text{OMe}$, $R^2 = -\text{CH}_3$ (73%)
 (c) $R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{Ph}$ (80%)
 (d) $R^1 = -\text{OMe}$, $R^2 = \text{Ph}$ (76%)
 (e) $R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = -\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ (70%)
 (f) $R^1 = -\text{OMe}$, $R^2 = -\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ (76%)

Scheme 2. Reagents and conditions : (i) AIBN, $n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$, $\text{Na}(\text{CN})\text{BH}_3$, benzene, reflux, 4–5 h.

We have achieved the regioselective synthesis of tetracyclic [6,6] pyranothiopyran by aryl radical cyclization²³. The starting materials 4-aryloxymethyl-7-methylthiopyrano[3,2-c]pyran-5-ones **7a-f** when refluxed in dry benzene with tributyl tin(IV) hydride in the presence of azoisobutyronitrile (AIBN) as an initiator for 4–5 h afforded the cyclized products **8a-f** in 75–80% yields (Scheme 3).

	R^1	R^2	R^3	Yield (%)
4(a)	H	H	H	75
(b)	Me	H	H	78
(c)	H	OMe	H	75
(d)		$-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4^b$	H	80
(e)	H	Me	H	75 (3 : 1) ^a
(f)	H	Me	Me	70 (2.3 : 1) ^a

^aDiastereomer ratio determined from the ^1H NMR spectrum.

^bBenzo.

Scheme 3. Reagents and conditions : (i) $n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$, AIBN, C_6H_6 , reflux, 4–5 h.

We have also carried out similar radical reaction with coumarin containing substrates²⁴. The radical precursors 4-aryloxymethyl pyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-5-(2H)-ones **9a-f** were refluxed in benzene under nitrogen atmosphere with tri-*n*-butyl tinchloride and sodium cyanoborohydride in the presence of a catalytic amount of azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) for 4–5 h to give cyclic products **10a-f** (Scheme 4).

3.1. Synthesis of spiroheterocycles :

We have also synthesized various spiroheterocycles **15a,b**²⁵ by the tri-*n*-butyltin hydride-induced radical cyclization of 5-(*o*-bromoaryloxymethylene)-6,7,8-trihydropyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-diones **11a,b**. The formation of the products **12a,b** from **11a,b** may be explained by the formation of an aryl radical **13**, followed by cyclization, to give the spirocyclic radical

	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Yield (%)
10(a)	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	82 (95 : 5)
(b)	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	79 (47 : 53)
(c)	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	76 (50 : 50)
(d)	H	H	CH ₃	80 (50 : 50)
(e)	CH ₃	H	H	70 (45 : 55)
(f)	H	H	H	75 (50 : 50)

Scheme 4. Reagents and conditions : (i) ⁿBu₃SnCl, Na(CN)BH₃, AIBN, C₆H₆, reflux, N₂ atmosphere, 4–5 h.

Scheme 5. Reagents and conditions : (i) ⁿBu₃SnCl, Na(CN)BH₃, AIBN, PhH, reflux, 4 h.

14, which may then give the final spiroheterocycles **12a,b** (Scheme 5).

The aryl radical cyclization of a range of 6-(2'-bromophenoxy)methyl-1,3-dimethyluracils **15a-g** with tributyltin chloride and sodium cyanoborohydride in the presence of AIBN for 4 h furnished exclusively the '5-*exo*' cyclization products, 1,3-dimethylspiro[pyrimidine-6,3'-2',3'-tetrahydrobenzofuran]-2,4-diones²⁶ **16a-g** in 92–95% yields (Scheme 6).

The regioselective formation of 5-membered heterocyclic ring can be explained by the application of the FMO theory. Aryl radicals are high-energy species and hence are nucleophilic in character. The presence of highly electron withdrawing carbonyl group confers considerable electrophilic character to the C-6 position of the uracil moiety.

Thus in the case of nucleophilic radical **17**, FMO theory suggests that the mode of ring closure is largely deter-

- 16(a)** $R^1 = R^2 = H, R^3 = Me$ (95%)
(b) $R^1 = R^3 = H, R^2 = Me$ (92%)
(c) $R^1 = Me, R^2 = R^3 = H$ (92%)
(d) $R^1 = R^2 = H, R^3 = OMe$ (94%)
(e) $R^1 = R^3 = Me, R^2 = H$ (92%)
(f) $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = H$ (94%)
(g) $R^1, R^2 = -5,6\text{-phenylene}, R^3 = H$ (95%)

Scheme 6. Reagents and conditions : (i) $n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}, \text{Na}(\text{CN})\text{BH}_3, \text{AIBN}, \text{PhH}, \text{reflux}, \text{N}_2$ atmosphere.

mined by the interaction between the radical SOMO (\equiv HOMO) and the alkene LUMO of the acceptor (electron deficient centre) and accordingly more favourable bond formation occurs between the radical centre (nucleophilic) and C_6 of the uracil ring for '5-*exo*' product **16a-g** (Scheme 7).

A number of *spiro* heterocyclic compounds **21a-f** have been regioselectively synthesized²⁷ in excellent yield by the $n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$ -AIBN mediated radical cyclization of 4-(2'-bromoaryloxymethyl)-1-methylquinolin-2(1*H*)-ones **20a-f** in refluxing benzene under nitrogen atmosphere for 4 h (Scheme 8).

Scheme 7

	R^1	R^2	R^3	R^4	Yield (%)
21(a)	H	H	OCH ₃	H	95
(b)	5,6-phenylene		H	H	95
(c)	H	H	3,4-phenylene		95
(d)	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	92
(e)	H	H	CH ₃	H	90
(f)	H	H	H	H	90

Scheme 8. Reagents and conditions : (i) $n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}, \text{AIBN}, \text{benzene}, \text{N}_2, \text{reflux}, 4 \text{ h}$.

Recently, we have also synthesised²⁸ spiro[chroman-3,3'(2'*H*)-benzofurans] **23a-f** in 60–75% yields from a number of 3-(2-bromophenoxy)methylcoumarins **22a-f** with tributyltin chloride and sodium cyanoborohydride in refluxing benzene for 7–10 h under nitrogen, in the presence of catalytic amount of AIBN (Scheme 9).

The formation of the spiro furan ring in compounds **23a-f** from **22a-f** can be explained by 5-*exo*-trig radical cyclization of the initially generated aryl radical onto the double bond of the coumarin moiety. Although both 5-

- (a) $R^1 = R^2 = H, R^3 = Me$ (72%)
 (b) $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = H$ (75%)
 (c) $R^1 = R^3 = H, R^2 = Me$ (65%)
 (d) $R^1 = R^2 = H, R^3 = OMe$ (68%)
 (e) $R^1 = Me, R^2 = R^3 = H$ (64%)
 (f) $R^1 = R^3 = Me, R^2 = H$ (60%)

Scheme 9. Reagents and conditions : (i) ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$, $\text{Na}(\text{CN})\text{BH}_3$, AIBN, benzene, reflux, 7–10 h.

exo and 6-*endo* cyclization are possible, in spite of our best efforts, by varying the reaction conditions, we could not generate the 6-*endo*-trig cyclized product or the corresponding lactone of compound **22**. The reason for the exclusive formation of 5-*exo* cyclization product is not clear. The stability of the intermediate benzylic radical may facilitate the formation of the spiro-benzofuran ring.

Deoxygenation of a carbonyl group giving the corresponding saturated hydrocarbon is a frequently encountered process in organic syntheses²⁹. The conversion of a lactone carbonyl into a cyclic ether by employing certain Lewis acid-hydride complexes is well established in literature³⁰. In such reactions, the *in situ* generated diborane in the presence of the Lewis acid presumably facilitates the deoxygenation reaction through the formation of an oxonium ion intermediate³¹. Although $\text{Na}(\text{CN})\text{BH}_3$ in the presence of a Lewis acid can deoxygenate carbonyl groups³², the reaction fails with lactones.

The radical cyclisation³³ of 3-(2'-bromobenzyloxy)-quinolin-2-ones **24a-d** and 3-(2'-bromobenzyloxy)-benzopyran-7-ones **24e,f** in the presence of ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ - $\text{Na}(\text{CN})\text{BH}_3$ -AIBN afforded spiro-quinolone and spiro-coumarin derivatives **25a-f** in 80–85% yields (Scheme 10).

Recently, we have also carried out the radical cyclization of substrates containing pyran-2-one moiety³⁴. For this purpose 6-[(2-bromophenoxy)methyl]-4-methoxy-

- 25(a)** X = NEt, R = H (80%)
 (b) X = NEt, R = OMe (82%)
 (c) X = NMe, R = H (84%)
 (d) X = NMe, R = OMe (80%)
 (e) X = -O-, R = H (85%)
 (f) X = -O-, R = OMe (84%)

Scheme 10. Reagents and conditions : (i) ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$, $\text{Na}(\text{CN})\text{BH}_3$, AIBN, benzene, reflux, 4–5 h.

pyran-2-ones **26a-e** were synthesized in 77–89% yields from 6-(bromomethyl)-4-methoxy-2-pyranone and 2-bromophenols.

The substrates **26a-e** were refluxed in dry toluene with tributyl tin(IV) hydride in the presence of azoisobutyronitrile (AIBN) as an initiator for 3–4 h to give the cyclized products **27a-e** in 68–79% yields (Scheme 11).

	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Yield (%)
27(a)	H	H	H	79
(b)	Me	H	H	74
(c)	H	Me	H	68
(d)	Me	H	Me	71
(e)	H	H	OCH ₃	76

Scheme 11. Reagents and conditions : (i) ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$, AIBN, toluene, reflux, 3–4 h, N_2 atmosphere.

We have recently described³⁵ the regioselective unusual formation of spirocyclic 4-{2'-benzo(2',3'-dihydro)furo}-9-methyl-2,3,9-trihydrothiopyrano[2,3-*b*]indole by 4-*exo*-trig aryl radical cyclization and rearrangement. The required precursors 4-(2'-bromoaryloxy-methylene)-9-methyl-2,3,9-trihydrothiopyrano[2,3-

	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	Yield (%)
30(a)	H	H	H	H	80
(b)	Me	H	H	H	77
(c)	H	H	Me	H	80
(d)	Me	H	Me	H	78
(e)	H	H	-Ph-		76
(f)	-Ph-		H	H	75

Scheme 12

b]indoles **29a-f** were synthesized in 80–86% yield by the *thio*-Claisen rearrangement of 2-(4'-aryloxybut-2'-ynylthio)-1-methylindoles **28a-f**. The products **29a-f** contain a suitably placed *o*-bromoaryl group with respect to the double bond of the enol ether. Therefore, compounds **29a-f** were treated with ⁿBu₃SnH (1.1 equiv.) in toluene at 80 °C in the presence of a radical initiator AIBN (0.5 equiv.) for 3–4 h to give the unusual products **30a-f** in 75–80% yields (Scheme 12).

The formation of the products **30** is explicable by a 4-

exo-trig cyclization of the initially generated aryl radical **31** at the enol ether part of the diene to give the more stable radical **32**. The stability is due to the overlapping of the *p*-orbital of the radical center of **32** with the neighboring π -system of the indole moiety. The highly strained oxetene ring may undergo ring opening leading to the formation of a resonance stabilized aryloxy radical **34**. The aryloxy radical **34** may then undergo 5-*endo-trig* cyclization to give stable benzylic radical **35** followed by abstraction of a hydrogen radical to afford the unusual product **30** (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13. Mechanism of aryl radical cyclization.

4. Synthesis of nitrogen heterocycles

Recently considerable attention has been directed towards the synthesis of nitrogen containing heterocycles by free radical cyclization³⁶. Nitrogen containing heterocycles as recognized pharmacophores have received great attention in drug discovery and lead optimization³⁷. In addition to traditional cyclization, cyclization of nitrogen radicals or nitrogen containing carbon radicals is the new approach to *N*-heterocycles. Between these two radical reactions, the latter one is more general because carbon radicals are easy to generate and is a well-established process³⁸.

Bowman *et al.* reported³⁹ the alkyl radical cyclizations onto imino group. Ryu *et al.* elaborated⁴⁰ the fact that 5-*exo*/6-*endo* type of acyl radical cyclization onto N=C furnished 2-pyrrolidinones through selective 5-*exo* manner. Recently, they also observed⁴¹ that 5-*exo*/6-*endo* type of vinyl radical cyclization onto aldimine N=C proceeds selectively in a 6-*endo* manner to produce methylenepiperidines. Naito *et al.*⁴² have exemplified the radical cyclization of various oxime ether and hydrazones. Using this methodology they have successfully synthesized cyclic amino acid by a combination of sulfanyl radical addition-cyclization of oxime ether or hydrazones connected with alkenes and subsequent conversion of phenylsulfamethyl unit to a carboxyl group.

Radical addition onto C-2, C-3 and C-4 of quinolone has all been shown to proceed under neutral conditions⁴³. In each case formation of heteroaromatic products, rather than dihydroquinolines, was observed by oxidative tin hydride pathway.

Aryl radicals generated by the homolysis of Ar-Br bond by ⁿBu₃SnH-AIBN have been used extensively as the key step in the establishment of Caryl-Calkyl bond. This method has been applied to construct a variety of system such as dihydroindoles⁴⁴, benzofuran⁴⁵, tetrahydro-β-naphthol⁴⁶ and oxyindoles⁴⁷. Radical cyclizations of *N*-vinyl systems have been extensively used for the synthesis of nitrogen heterocycles⁴⁸. A novel radical cyclization involving ⁿBu₃SnH has been demonstrated⁴⁹ to form tri- and tetracyclic ring systems related to the Amaryllicaceae or Erythrina family of alkaloids.

Many isoquinolinone derivatives possess biological activity⁵⁰. Recently, we have developed a facile route to the synthesis of isoquinoline derivatives fused with pyrimidine at C-5 and C-6 positions by regioselective aryl radical cyclization to *N*-vinyl system⁵¹.

Substrate **36a-f** when treated with tri-*n*-butyltin chloride, sodium cyanoborohydride and azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) in refluxing degassed benzene under nitrogen for 5 h, afforded exclusively the tetrahydropyridine derivative **37a-f**⁵² in 80–85% yields (Scheme 14).

- (a) R¹ = Et, R² = Me, R³ = H (85%)
 (b) R¹ = Et, R² = Me, R³ = OMe (80%)
 (c) R¹ = R² = Me, R³ = H (83%)
 (d) R¹ = R² = Me, R³ = OMe (84%)
 (e) R¹ = R² = Et, R³ = H (84%)
 (f) R¹ = R² = Et, R³ = OMe (85%)

Scheme 14. Radical cyclization onto uracil moiety.

The formation of a six-membered heterocyclic ring **37** from the substrates **36** may be easily explained by the initial formation of the aryl radical **38**, followed by a 6-*endo* ring closure to give a tertiary radical **39**, which may then accept a hydrogen radical to afford the final products **37**. In an alternative route, the aryl radical may undergo a 5-*exo* ring closure to generate a spiroheterocyclic radical **40**⁵³, which may be converted into the tertiary radical **39** by a neophyl rearrangement⁵⁴ (Scheme 15).

An interesting feature of this reaction sequence is that the usual aerial oxidation in this type of cyclization with ⁿBu₃SnH is not observed and the dihydro compounds are isolated in excellent yields. The usual course during this type of cyclization is that the initially formed dihydro products give oxidized products by aerial oxidation, i.e. an oxidation step in the ⁿBu₃SnH-mediated cyclisation⁵⁵.

Another interesting 6-*endo* aryl radical cyclization followed by oxidation affording isoquinoline derivatives fused with coumarin at 3,4 positions were observed in case of substrate 4-[*N*-(2'-bromobenzyl), *N*-methyl] amino coumarins **42a-h**. The tertiary amines **42a-h** were refluxed in degassed dry benzene under nitrogen with tri-*n*-butyl tin chloride and sodium cyanoborohydride in the presence of radical initiator AIBN (0.5–0.6 equiv.) for 3–4 h to give the cyclized products **43a-h**^{56a} in 65–68% yields (Scheme 16).

Scheme 15. Mechanism for the formation of 6-membered product.

- 43(a) $R^1 = R^3 = R^4 = H$, $R^2 = CMe_3$ (65%)
 (b) $R^1 = R^3 = H$, $R^2 = CMe_3$, $R^4 = OMe$ (67%)
 (c) $R^1 = R^3 = R^4 = H$, $R^2 = Me$ (70%)
 (d) $R^1 = R^3 = H$, $R^2 = CH_3$, $R^4 = OMe$ (67%)
 (e) $R^1 = R^2 = R^4 = H$, $R^3 = Me$ (66%)
 (f) $R^1 = R^2 = H$, $R^3 = CH_3$, $R^4 = OMe$ (69%)
 (g) $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = R^4 = H$ (68%)
 (h) $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = H$, $R^4 = OMe$ (65%)

Scheme 16. Radical cyclization onto coumarin moiety.

Recently, we have also reported^{56b} the regioselective synthesis of 6a,7,8,12b-tetrahydro-6H-chromeno[3,4-c]quinolin-6-ones **45a-f** by aryl radical cyclization of 3-(2-bromoanilinomethyl)coumarins **44a-f** (Scheme 17). But in this system the usual aerial oxidation was not observed, only the reduced products were isolated in 74–88% yields.

5. Synthesis of sulphur heterocycles

A few years ago, Ponaras *et al.* reported⁵⁷ the ⁿBu₃SnH mediated radical cyclization of sulfur containing system 2-(ω-haloalkylthio)enones to produce predominantly the fused thiapolycycloalkanones. Recently, Della *et al.* re-

ported⁵⁸ the cyclization of 2-thia- and 2-sulfonyl-5-hexenyl radicals and obtained mixtures containing substantial quantities of both the 5-endo and 6-exo products, respectively. They also pointed out⁵⁹ the regioselectivity of the ring closure of 2-thia-, 2-sulfinyl and 2-sulfonyl-5-methyl-5-hexenyl radicals. In case of 5-hexenyl radicals, the sulfinyl-substituted species showed unexpected regioselectivity relative to its analogues.

Recently, we have described⁶⁰ a simple convergent synthesis of the *cis*-benzothiopyrano[3,2-*c*]benzopyran-7(2*H*)-ones **47a-f**, through the implementation of a regioselective 6-endo-trig aryl radical cyclization of the

	R	R ¹	Yield (%)
45(a)	H	H	81
(b)	H	CH ₃	85
(c)	H	C ₂ H ₅	88
(d)	CH ₃	H	74
(e)	CH ₃	CH ₃	82
(f)	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	78

Scheme 17. Reagents and conditions : (i) ⁿBu₃SnH, AIBN, toluene, 80 °C, 2–2.5 h, (ii) ⁿBu₃SnH, Na(CN)BH₃, AIBN, toluene, 60 °C, 1 h.

respective 4-(2'-bromobenzyl)thiobenzopyran-7-ones **46a-f** with tributyltin hydride in the presence of AIBN (Scheme 18).

	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	Yield (%)
47(a)	H	H	H	OCH ₃	75
(b)	H	H	H	H	72
(c)	H	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	72
(d)	H	CH ₃	H	H	70
(e)	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	OCH ₃	74
(f)	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	70

Scheme 18. Reagents and conditions : (i) ⁿBu₃SnH, AIBN, benzene, reflux, 1 h.

The exclusive formation of 6-membered heterocyclic ring in products **47a-f** from the substrates **46a-f** can be best explained by a 6-*endo* ring closure of the intermediate aryl radical on to the pyrone double bond of the coumarin moiety.

The tin hydride mediated radical cyclization of a number of sulfides and sulfones under mild and neutral con-

dition have also been investigated, where some amount of β -scission product was obtained for the sulfide precursors. The sulfides 4-(2'-bromobenzylsulfanyl)-1-alkyl-1H-quinolin-2-ones **48a-d** (X = S) and the corresponding sulfones 4-(2'-bromobenzylsulfonyl)-1-alkyl-1H-quinolin-2-ones **48e-h** (X = SO₂) were treated under reflux with ⁿBu₃SnH-AIBN in dry degassed benzene under nitrogen atmosphere to give regioselectively quinolone-annulated sulfur heterocycles⁶¹ (Scheme 19).

	X	R ₁	R ₂	Yield (%)
49(a)	S	CH ₃	H	65
(b)	S	CH ₃	OCH ₃	63
(c)	S	C ₂ H ₅	H	65
(d)	S	C ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	60
(e)	SO ₂	CH ₃	H	90
(f)	SO ₂	CH ₃	OCH ₃	88
(g)	SO ₂	C ₂ H ₅	H	85
(h)	SO ₂	C ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	80

Scheme 19. Reagents and conditions : ⁿBu₃SnH, AIBN, benzene, reflux, 1–4 h.

However, the 5-*exo*-cyclization followed by a neophyl rearrangement is highly unlikely with the present system. It is known that β -fragmentation of alkyl thiyl radicals are very fast⁶² ($> 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$) compared to neophyl-type rearrangements, which are much slower⁶³ (about $10^3 \text{ s}^{-1} - 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Therefore, neophyl rearrangement of radical **52** cannot compete with the β -fragmentation reaction, which would lead to another product. The other reason is that the intermediate tertiary radical **51** is more stable than the spiro heterocyclic radical **52** since sulfur stabilised the adjacent radical centre by its greater polarisation⁶⁴. The stabilised conformational intermediate radical **51** give preferably *cis*, the usual reduced product **49** (Scheme 20).

Recently, we have also described the regioselective synthesis⁶⁵ of benzofuran-annulated six-membered sulfur heterocycles by aryl radical cyclization. The substrates

Scheme 20

56a,b were treated at 80 °C in dry degassed toluene under a nitrogen atmosphere with ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$ in the presence of AIBN as radical initiator for 4 h to afford the cyclic product **57a,b** in 90% and 95% yields, respectively, along with a small amount of debrominated products. This debromination was inhibited by the conversion of the sulfides to the corresponding-sulfones. Exposure of the sulfones **56c,d** to ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$ under the same reaction conditions as described above afforded the cyclized heterocyclic sulfones **57c,d** in 96% and 93% yields, respectively (Scheme 21).

	X	R	Yield (%)
57(a)	S	H	90
(b)	S	OMe	95
(c)	SO ₂	H	96
(d)	SO ₂	OMe	93

Scheme 21. Reagents and conditions : (i) ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$, AIBN, toluene, N₂ atmosphere, reflux, 4 h.

We have also extended this methodology to the synthesis of quinolone annulated-sulfur heterocycles. When the radical precursors 4-(2'-bromothioarylmethyl)-1-methylquinolin-2(1*H*)-ones **58a-c** and the corresponding sulfones **58d-f** were heated in dry toluene at 80 °C under a nitrogen atmosphere with ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$ and AIBN for 1 h, furnished the cyclic products **59a-f** in 90–96% yields⁶⁶ (Scheme 22).

	X	R	Yield (%)
59(a)	S	Me	90
(b)	S	Et	92
(c)	S	H	91
(d)	SO ₂	Me	95
(e)	SO ₂	Et	96
(f)	SO ₂	H	95

Scheme 22. Reagents and conditions : (i) ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$, toluene, 80 °C, N₂ atmosphere, 1 h.

Recently, the regiochemical study of ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$ -AIBN mediated aryl radical cyclization of different, 3-(2-bromophenylsulfonylethyl)coumarins (**60a-c**), 3-(2-bromophenylsulfonylethyl)coumarins (**60d-f**), have been investigated with the formation of different [6,6] fused and spirocyclic sulfur heterocycles³⁴. Compounds **60a-c** were heated at 55–60 °C with ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$ in dry degassed toluene in the presence of a catalytic amount of AIBN for 1 h, to afford the [6,6] fused cyclic products **61a-c** in 72–88% yields along with spiro-cyclic products **62a** (20%) and **62b** (5%) in case of substrates **60a** and **60b**. Sulfones **60d-f** when subjected to radical cyclization under similar condition as described above furnished spirocyclic compounds **62d-f**, exclusively, in 76–85% yields (Scheme 23).

Scheme 23. Reagents and conditions : (i) ${}^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnH}$, AIBN, toluene, N₂ atmosphere 55–60 °C, 1 h.

The formation of the products **61** and **62** can be easily explained by assuming a 6-*endo* and 5-*exo* cyclization of the aryl radical respectively onto the double bond of coumarin moiety. In the case of phenylsulfonylethyl congener **60d-f**, the generated aryl radical undergo 5-*exo* cyclization exclusively to produce the spirocyclic products **62d-f**. The neophyl rearrangement path is unlikely with the present system because the stability and non-

nucleophilicity⁶⁷ of the intermediate benzylic radical, due to excellent overlapping⁶⁸ of *p*-orbital of the radical center with the adjacent aromatic π -system might prevent further attack to produce the intermediate cyclohexadienyl radical.

6. Thiophenol mediated radical cyclization

The radical reactions of some thiol esters were carried out by adding a benzene solution of PhSH and AIBN under refluxing conditions by Benati *et al.*⁶⁹. The cyclised indanone and tetralone in *ca.* 96 : 4 ratio (overall 73% yield), along with comparable amounts of the (*E*)- and (*Z*)-dihydrothiophene were obtained. Small amounts of the (*E*)- and (*Z*)-vinyl sulphide adduct were also isolated. Crich *et al.* prepared⁷⁰ the iodothioli ester precursors by the reaction of (iodophenyl)ethanethiol with appropriate acyl chlorides. Benati *et al.* have utilised⁷¹ this idea to prepare thiophene by the reaction of thiol ester with R'SH and AIBN in refluxing benzene. Naito *et al.* investigated⁷² the thiol mediated radical cyclisation of various oxime ethers and obtained a mixture of the *cis* and *trans* compounds in combined yield.

Recently, we have reported the regioselective synthesis of dihydrofurocoumarins and dihydropyranocoumarins by thiol mediated radical cyclization reactions⁷³. The radical precursors coumarin-4-yl-prop-2-ynyl ethers **63a-d**, were refluxed in dry *t*-butanol under nitrogen atmosphere with PhSH (2 equiv.) and AIBN (1.5 equiv.) for 1 h to afford dihydropyranocoumarin derivatives **64a-d** in 80–88% yields. When the same reactions were carried out in dry benzene instead of dry *t*-butanol, totally different products **65a-d**, were obtained in 78–88% yields (Scheme 24).

Scheme 24. Reagents and conditions : (i) PhSH, AIBN, *t*-butanol, reflux, 1 h; (ii) PhSH, AIBN, benzene, reflux, 40–50 min.

Scheme 25

A clear trend related to the solvent polarity or ability to form hydrogen bonds accounts for the outcomes of these experiments. In polar *t*-butanol, thiophenol catalyzed the Claisen rearrangement of **63** followed by addition of a thiyl radical in the presence of AIBN, to afford **64**.

The formation of the products **65** from **63** may be explained by the generation of alkenyl radical **66** by radical addition of thiophenol to the terminal alkyne **63**. The alkenyl radical **66** may undergo either a 4-*exo trig* or a 5-*endo trig* cyclization at the double bond of the pyrone ring of the coumarin moiety. A 5-*endo trig* cyclization of radical **66** may produce the intermediate radical **67** whilst 4-*exo trig* cyclization may give the spiroheterocyclic radical **68**, followed by neophyl rearrangement⁵⁴ to radical intermediate **67**. Oxidative elimination of hydrogen from **67** may afford **65** (Scheme 25).

71(a) R = CH₃, R¹ = H (82%)

(b) R = R¹ = H (78%)

(c) R = C₂H₅, R¹ = H (80%)

(d) R = H, R¹ = CH₃ (76%)

Scheme 26. Reagents and conditions : (i) *t*-butanol, PhSH, AIBN, reflux, 20–25 min.

We have also extended our efforts in the regioselective synthesis of indole-annulated sulfur heterocycles by tandem cyclization mediated by thiophenol⁷⁴. When sulfides **70a-d** were treated with PhSH (2 equiv.) in refluxing *tert*-butanol in the presence of a radical initiator AIBN (1.5 equiv.) for 20 min to give tetrahydrothiopyrano [2,3-*b*]indole derivatives **71a-d** in 76–82% yields (Scheme 26).

The reductive addition of a thiophenyl radical at the alkyne terminals can generate the alkenyl radical **72**. These alkenyl radical **72**, via a 5-*endo trig* cyclization could produce the intermediate radical **73** whilst a 4-*exo trig* cyclization followed by neophyl rearrangement would produce radical intermediate **73**. The formation of products **71** from **70** is explicable by abstraction of hydrogen radical by the intermediate radical **72** to afford intermediate **76** followed by intramolecular addition of the enamine (indole or indole with electron donating group) to the thioether via an ionic pathway. This is possible due to the availability of a nitrogen lone pair (Scheme 27).

With a view to investigate the participation of the lone pair of the nitrogen of the indole moiety in the cyclization we prepared substrates **78a,b** by the reaction of compound **70b** with benzoyl chloride and acetyl chloride, respectively. Compounds **78a,b** were treated as in the case of compounds **70a-d** to afford products **79a,b** in 68% and 65% yields, respectively (Scheme 28).

When electron-withdrawing groups are attached at the indole nitrogen, the pyrrole ring of indole becomes much

Scheme 27

Scheme 28. Reagents and conditions : (i) PhCOCl or CH₃COCl dry DCM, Bu₄NHSO₄, NaOH (powder), stirring, 1 h, 0 °C; (ii) *t*-butanol, PhSH, AIBN, reflux, 25 min.

less aromatic and hence more alkene-like, thereby facilitating the radical cyclization to form **75** (Scheme 27) followed by two successive [1,3] proton exchange to afford products **79** (Scheme 29). Aromatisation of indole moiety may be the driving force for the formation of products **79** from **78**.

In continuation of our study on thiophenol mediated

radical cyclization reactions, recently we have reported the thiophenol mediated 8-*endo* radical cyclization towards the synthesis of medium-sized cyclic ethers⁷⁵. The radical precursors **81a-e** on treatment with 2 equiv. of thiophenol in the presence of radical initiator AIBN in refluxing *t*-butanol to give the cyclized products **82a-e** in 82–92% yields. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Scheme 29

Scheme 30

 Table 1. Sulfanyl radical addition and cyclization of **81a-e**^a

Starting materials (81)	Products (82)	Yields (%)
		83
		82
		84
		85
		92

^aReagents and conditions : dry *t*-butanol, PhSH, AIBN, reflux, 2 h.

The phenyl thiyl radical, generated from thiophenol and AIBN, is added to the terminal alkyne to form vinyl radical **83**. Intramolecularly, this vinyl radical may undergo an 8-*endo trig* cyclization with adjacent alkene to form intermediate radical **84** which on abstraction of a H

radical from thiophenol afford the products **82** (Scheme 30).

The literature on the synthesis of heterocycles by radical cyclization is vast and it is beyond the scope of this lecture. Therefore, only the introduction, mechanism and authors' own work have been presented. Although the radical reaction has been studied extensively but we believe that it still offers challenges to the synthetic organic chemists.

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Majumdar : Regioselective synthesis of bioactive heterocycles by radical cyclization

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